

Clinical Presentation, Surgical Approaches, and Outcomes of Third Ventricular Colloid Cysts: A Retrospective Single-Center Study from Oman

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Introduction

Colloid cysts are intracranial lesions that arise from the roof of the third ventricle around the foramen of Monro. Obstructive hydrocephalus is the primary cause of their clinical manifestations. Despite their recognized clinical significance, literature on postoperative complications following colloid cyst resection remains scarce in Oman and the Middle East region. As such, this study aims to address this gap by evaluating surgical outcomes and complication profiles within an Omani cohort.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective case series was conducted at Sultan Qaboos University Hospital, Oman. Medical records of patients who underwent surgical management for intracranial colloid cysts between September 2011 and August 2025 were reviewed. Sixteen patients met the inclusion criteria.

Results

The cohort included 16 patients (10 males, 6 females) with a median age of 30.5 years. Most patients (43.8%) presented to the emergency department, and headache was the most common presenting symptom (87.5%). Hydrocephalus was present in 75% of cases. Surgical approaches included transcallosal (75%), endoscopic (18.75%), and transcortical (6.25%). Four patients (25%) experienced no postoperative complications; nine (56.3%) developed minor complications and three (18.8%) developed major complications, based on clinical severity and the need for further intervention. One patient (6.25%) died postoperatively. Postoperative relief of hydrocephalus was observed in most patients.

Conclusion

Surgical management was generally associated with relief of hydrocephalus and acceptable outcomes in most patients, although significant complications may still occur. These findings highlight the importance of early recognition and timely neuroimaging in patients with chronic, atypical, or progressive headache to reduce the risk of acute neurological deterioration and optimize outcomes.

Keywords

Colloid cyst; third ventricle; hydrocephalus; headache; surgical outcomes; postoperative complications; retrospective case series; Oman.